

HALOGENATION. PART XVIII. HALOGENATION OF ETHYLBENZENE.

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The halogenation of ethylbenzene has been studied before and according to the conditions of the experiments which are well known, nuclear or side-chain substitution products are obtained.

We have studied the action of bromine and iodine on ethylbenzene in presence of fuming nitric acid, nitrosulphonic acid or their mixtures and have obtained both nuclear or side-chain derivatives. Ethylbenzene, when chlorinated in presence of iodine, yields 4-chloroethylbenzene in good yield. Using these methods of halogenation, we have obtained the following hitherto unknown halogen derivatives of ethylbenzene: 4-iodo-3-bromoethylbenzene, 4-chloro-3-bromoethylbenzene, and 4-chloro-1' (?)-bromoethylbenzene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Chloroethylbenzene.—Dry chlorine was passed for 3 hours through ethylbenzene (15 c.c.) in a flask, protected from light either by covering it thickly with soot or with black cloth, in presence of iodine (0.1 g.). The product was washed, dried over calcium chloride, filtered and distilled. A small quantity of unused ethylbenzene distilled over first and then a liquid (11 c.c.) at 180-181°. It gives on oxidation with nitric acid 4-chlorobenzoic acid.

1'-Bromoethylbenzene.—Ethylbenzene (10 c.c.) was taken in a flask which was directly exposed to the sun and then nitrosulphonic acid mixture (about 8 drops) and afterwards bromine (2 c.c.) dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) were added drop by drop and the flask shaken vigorously after each addition. When the whole of the bromine solution was added, the flask was allowed to stand in sunlight for a further period of 1 hour after which it was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour more. The contents were washed with water, dried and distilled. Unused ethylbenzene (3 c.c.) first distilled over and then 4-bromoethylbenzene (a small quantity only) at 188-198°, leaving

behind a somewhat viscous liquid which decomposes on further heating. This fraction distills undecomposed at 94-95°/10 mm. It is found to be *l'*-bromoethylbenzene, yield 4 g.

4-Bromoethylbenzene and 2 : 4-Dibromoethylbenzene.—The preceding experiment was repeated keeping the flask covered with black cloth instead of being exposed to the sun. The products were separated as described above and distilled at the ordinary pressure when 4-bromoethylbenzene (6 c.c.) distilled over. By brominating ethylbenzene (20 c.c.) with excess of bromine (12 c.c.), a solid compound (8.5 g.) was obtained which crystallises from alcohol in needles, m.p. 70-72°. On oxidation this compound gives 2 : 4-dibromobenzoic acid, m.p. 167°. Hence the new compound is 2 : 4-dibromoethylbenzene. (Found : Br, 60.18. $C_8H_8Br_2$ requires Br, 60.58 per cent). It is sparingly soluble in rectified spirit, easily soluble in ether, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and chloroform.

4-Iodoethylbenzene.—Ethylbenzene (10 c.c.), iodine (10 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) were heated with a reflux condenser on a water-bath and a mixture of fuming nitric and nitrosulphonic acid (6 c.c.) was gradually added. After heating for 4 hours, the reaction product was washed free from acid, dried and distilled at 112-113°/20 mm., yield 10 g.

In this experiment in place of a mixture of fuming nitric and nitrosulphonic acid, fuming nitric acid (3 c.c.) alone, or a mixture of fuming nitric and fuming sulphuric acid (3 c.c. each) or sodium nitrite (10 g.) and fuming sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) can also be employed.

4-Iodo-3-bromoethylbenzene.—4-Iodoethylbenzene (5 c.c.), bromine (3.3 c.c.) and iodine (0.1 g.) were heated on a water-bath, when there was a brisk evolution of hydrogen bromide. When the reaction was over after 3 or 4 hours, the contents of the flask were cooled, washed with water, sodium carbonate solution and finally again with water, dried and allowed to stand. Needle shaped crystals (3.4 g.) gradually separated out, m.p. 88-89°. It is soluble in alcohol, carbon tetrachloride, ether and chloroform. It gives on oxidation with chromic acid in acetic acid 4-iodo-3-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 239-40°. Hodgson and Beard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 27) gives 242-43° as the melting point of this compound. [Found : Total halogen calc. as Br, 59.1 (by analysis of silver halides) ; Br, 25.9 ; I, 40.1. C_8H_8BrI requires total halogen, 59.6 ; Br, 25.7 ; I, 40.8 per cent].

4-Chloro-3-bromoethylbenzene.—4-Chloroethylbenzene (10 c.c.) was treated with a solution of bromine (4 c.c.) in acetic acid (10 c.c.) in presence

of a trace of iodine and heated on a water-bath for 5 hours. The products were then cooled and washed with 1% sodium carbonate, dried and distilled at $143\text{--}44^{\circ}/10$ mm. The liquid (5 c.c.), on oxidation with concentrated nitric acid gives 4-chloro-3-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 213° . Cohen and Raper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 1269) gives 214° as the m.p. of this compound whereas Hodgson and Beard (*loc. cit.*) gives $215\text{--}16^{\circ}$. (Found: Total halogen calc. as Cl, 37.0; Cl, 16.7; Br, 35.1. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ClBr}$ requires total halogen calc. as Cl, 37.3; Cl, 16.2; Br, 36.4 per cent).

4-Chloro-1'-bromoethylbenzene.—4-Chloroethylbenzene (10 c.c.) was treated with a solution of bromine (5 c.c.) in chloroform (5 c.c.) in a silica flask and kept exposed to sunlight when a vigorous reaction set in with a considerable rise in temperature. When the action subsided, the products were washed, dried and distilled at $120\text{--}21^{\circ}/8$ mm. The liquid obtained (7 c.c.) gives on oxidation with concentrated nitric acid 4-chlorobenzoic acid, m.p. 243° . It is sparingly soluble in rectified spirit, easily soluble in ether, chloroform and benzene. (Found: Total halogen calc. as Cl, 37.1; Cl, 16.8; Br, 35.2. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ClBr}$ requires total halogen calc. as Cl, 37.3; Cl, 16.2; Br, 36.4 per cent).

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